

Insights to Inspire 2019 Blogs

In 2019 hubs that had shown the greatest improvement in the Common Metrics (IRB turnaround times, pilot publications and the careers of future researchers) were interviewed by the Center for Leading Innovation & Collaboration. The blogs below are a result of those interviews

Blog 1 – Insights to Inspire: Four Strategies for Improving IRB Turnaround Times

For many Clinical and Translational Science Award (CTSA) Program hubs, delays in Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval can feel like a translational roadblock on scientists' path to implementing research that may ultimately improve public health outcomes. However, as an essential part of ensuring the welfare of human research subjects, the IRB is crucial to maintaining the highest ethical standards in research. If hubs take the necessary steps to address researchers' pain points within their IRB approval process, they will be better positioned to realize goals for improvement and increase the effectiveness of the CTSA Program consortium overall.

In order to maximize the consortium's impact, NCATS has implemented the Common Metrics Initiative (CMI). The vision for NCATS' CMI is to use specific, common metrics to demonstrate and improve the impact of the CTSA Program. The CMI uses this set of metrics to help focus network and hub activities on making significant, measurable improvements in translational science and research, and workforce development.

Included in this set of metrics is the IRB Common Metric. This assesses the median number of calendar days from the date an application is received by the IRB to the date it is officially approved. In 2019, the Common Metrics Initiative released a Multi-Year Report that identifies the hubs with the most improvement in each of the three metrics for the measurement period of 2016-2017. For the IRB Common Metric, the University of Texas Medical College Branch (UTMB) Galveston and the University of Massachusetts Medical School (UMMS) were among the hubs with the greatest improvement in that period. Both institutions implemented several unique strategies to transform their IRB turnaround times and deliver an improved IRB common metric. Their strategies include:

1. *Encourage education and awareness*

In an effort to improve application turnaround times and overall efficiency, the UMMS IRB office and Center for Clinical and Translational Science (CCTS) teamed up to take a hard look at their approach to education. What they found was that the group training sessions they were using to educate investigators on how to work with the IRB were poorly attended, ineffective and left investigators with many questions about their specific research projects.

To address this, the IRB office implemented “Ask an Expert” sessions where investigators can sit one-on-one with IRB staff members to ask questions and get advice. These “Ask an Expert” sessions provide a personalized, proactive approach to educating investigators on what is needed to receive IRB approval, ensuring investigators are headed down the right path early in the process rather than making corrections after they are already headed down the wrong path. The IRB team at UMMS also drove education and awareness by developing a self-service “Getting Started” webpage and by gaining a presence at new faculty orientation where they were able to briefly introduce the board members, give an overview on how to work with the IRB and allow people to ask questions. This planted the seed with new investigators about the role of the IRB at UMMS. UMMS’ CCTS played a key role in garnering the necessary institutional support to drive these changes.

2. *More meetings make for more opportunities*

As the IRB office and the Institute for Translational Science at UTMB Galveston looked to make improvements to their IRB application process, their focus was on increasing opportunities for approval. Prior to 2016, the UTMB IRB only met once a month. In 2016, UTMB Galveston doubled that frequency to two IRB meetings twice a month. This small scheduling change packed a big punch. By doubling the frequency of the meetings, UTMB Galveston created more opportunities for investigators to gain feedback, make corrections and resubmit quickly, if their first submission was not accepted.

“Our mindset is that the IRB office should work with investigators, we shouldn’t be an obstacle,” said Gwen Baillargeon, Senior Biostatistician, UTMB Galveston. “When meetings were only once a month, we stood in the way of investigators completing their research. Now, instead of having to wait a full 30 days before their submission can be reviewed again, investigators now only have to wait two weeks.”

3. *Invest in your workforce*

One of the biggest challenges for UMMS’ IRB office was finding and retaining skilled IRB staff members. In the competitive Boston-area market, IRB experience is in high demand and the UMMS team found that they were frequently losing talented people to other institutions. The IRB office mitigated this rate of attrition by making two key changes. First, they worked with their HR department to add a rung to the career ladder. This created a place for employees to move up to once they were hired, thus creating more motivation for them to stay and continue to improve their skills. Second, the office did an in-depth assessment of their workforce and made changes to ensure they had the right number of people with the right skills in place. “By ensuring that we had the correct quantity of team members with the skills necessary to be successful in their position, we were able to decrease employee burnout by more evenly distributing workload,” said Allison Blodgett, IRB Director, UMMS.

UMMS also addressed the challenges they were experiencing in filling IRB leadership positions by putting a mentorship program in place. Through this program selected members of the committee were brought in on leadership tasks to groom them to run a meeting in the event that the chair/vice chair was absent or to fill in if one of the chairs stepped down. This gave committee members opportunities to learn and grow while ensuring little to no downtime in IRB operations in the event of a leadership transition.

4. *Change your reputation*

Both UMMS and UTMB Galveston emphasize the importance of generating an internal change in mindset within the IRB office and an external change in reputation. Instead of fostering a reputation that the IRB office is difficult to work with and a hurdle to overcome, these hubs made a conscious effort to streamline processes and make working with the IRB as easy as possible. For UTMB Galveston, the chief complaint that the IRB office received in 2012 was that investigators couldn't get any answers. The staff had gotten into the habit of saying no without providing any explanation or feedback on rejected applications. "Now we have the mindset of a customer service department," said Baillargeon. "By holding ourselves to a higher standard when interacting with investigators we were able to transform the reputation of our office to one investigators want to work with."

By measuring and tracking changes in IRB turnaround times, IRB offices are able to identify areas that need improvement and take the necessary steps to change. The good news is that IRB offices and CTSA Program hubs don't have to do it alone. They can gain insight and inspiration about how to bring about transformational changes by collaborating with and learning from other CTSA Program hubs.

Blog 2 – Insights to Inspire: The Four Stages of a Successful Pilot Funding Publication Program

As a key currency of the scientific community, publications are often used as a measurement of success for researchers and research institutions. Published research allows an expansive community of scientists, healthcare professionals, government workers and more to make data-driven decisions that will improve population and patient health outcomes. The Clinical and Translational Science Award (CTSA) Program, funded by the National Center for Advancing Translational Science (NCATS), seeks to drive the continued development of research through pilot funded projects that will yield tangible medical and population health interventions, which can then be disseminated through scientific literature.

In order to maximize the consortium's impact, NCATS created the Common Metrics Initiative (CMI). The vision for the CMI is to use specific, common metrics to demonstrate and improve the impact of the CTSA Program. The CMI, implemented by the Center for Leading Innovation and Collaboration (CLIC), uses this set of metrics to help focus network and hub activities on making significant, measurable improvements in translational science and research, and workforce development.

Included in this set of metrics is the Pilot Funding Publication Common Metric. This metric assesses the total number of scholarly publications resulting from pilot funded research at a CTSA Program hub each year. In 2019, the Common Metrics Initiative released a Multi-Year Report that identifies the hubs with the most improvement in each of the three metrics for the measurement period of 2016-2017. A selection of the hubs that saw the greatest improvement in their Pilot Funding Publication metric shared their strategies for making improvements across the four key stages of a successful Pilot Funding Publication Program and their advice for how others can implement similar changes.

Stage 1: Fund the right projects

To create this improvement, CTSI of Southeast Wisconsin took several steps to address their pilot funding process. One of the areas they focused on was how to select the right projects to receive funding in the first place. "We created a more cohesive and extensive review process that strategically assesses the potential of each project," said Dr. Reza Shaker, Principal Investigator and Director, CTSI of Southeast Wisconsin. "We also increased the number of reviewers for each application, emphasizing the importance of quality projects, not just the quantity of them."

As University of Miami looked to make improvements to their Pilot Funding Publication metric, they zeroed in on their approach to selecting the right projects to fund. "We have a rigorous review process in place and as a result we end up funding very high-quality research projects that often lead to high-quality publications," said Dr. Dalton Dietrich, Co-Investigator and Pilot Program Director, University of Miami. University of Miami also emphasizes the importance of being upfront with applicants about the

expectation of a scholarly outcome. By setting that expectation early and then checking in with researchers regularly throughout their project, University of Miami keeps the goal of publication at the forefront of awardees' minds.

University of Miami also found that, when possible, if they support pilots that focus on new or emerging health topics, there is greater potential to secure sizeable subsequent funding and additional publication by tapping into increased interest around a "trending" topic. "During the Zika outbreak in Florida, we awarded several innovative pilot projects that focused on the issue and this led to large amounts of additional federal and state funding for these projects as well as additional publications," said Rosalina Das, Senior Evaluation Manager, University of Miami. Despite being a smaller hub, such "the greater the risk, the greater the reward" strategies can also be applied at larger hubs to deliver similar results.

Stage 2: Support the researcher on his/her path to publication

University of Miami also attributes their improved Pilot Funding Publication Common Metric to the creation of multiple touchpoints with pilot funded researchers as they carry out their project. The hub has created a reputation among their pilot funded awardees as a resource for ongoing research support, grant writing guidance, letters of support, peer reviews, and more. Additionally, pilot funded researchers are given clear points of contact at the CTSI who they can reach out to with questions or concerns, making it easy to address issues when they arise and minimize any downtime in the research.

Michelle Miller and her team at Scripps Research Translational Institute took a similar approach to improving their hub's Pilot Funding Publication Common Metric saying, "by personalizing our interactions with pilot funded awardees, we were able to develop a rapport with them, making them feel comfortable enough with our team to air concerns and ask questions before major issues derailed their project."

To prevent struggling projects from falling through the cracks, Weill Medical College of Cornell's CTSC Common Metrics committee leveraged the investigator survey tool, PROMPTR. The team created a "needs page" that is sent to pilot funded researchers while their project is in-process. The form asks a series of questions to better understand the researcher's expectations for their project and what challenges they foresee. The page is then reviewed by the hub's PI. "The needs page generates a report for us that lists projects that are currently in the works, including descriptions and status updates, so that we can review and identify potential issues and offer interventions" said Elizabeth Wood, Co-Director, Biomedical Informatics, Weill Medical College of Cornell. For more information on how to leverage PROMPTR's needs pages at your own hub, please view [this webinar](#) overview from Weill Cornell and CLIC.

Stage 3: Ensure CTSA Program grant citation

Not only do multiple checkpoints with pilot funded awardees allow PIs to troubleshoot for potential issues with struggling projects, they also provide an opportunity to remind researchers about citing the CTSA grant number. Without proper citation of the grant number, not only is that hub not receiving credit for their role in funding the research, it makes it much less likely that evaluators will be able to find the publication when reporting on the hub's Common Metrics. "We make it a priority to share grant numbers early in an awardee's project," said Michelle Miller, Operations Manager, Scripps Research Translational Institute. "By providing researchers with the grant number up front and then sending frequent reminders, we were able to make significant strides with the accuracy of their citation."

Stage 4: Find the publication once it gets published

While it may seem simple, tracking publications that result from pilot funded projects can often be the most challenging part of securing a strong Pilot Funding Publication Common Metric. To help address this, the team at Weill Medical College of Cornell, led by Elizabeth Wood, developed PAIRS, a tool within WebCamp that proactively identifies publications potentially resulting from CTSC projects. It does so by issuing a broad search of PubMed and matching publications to pilot project titles based on search terms. "For each automated search, the tool generates a report that allows the user to review all publications found and either confirm it as an outcome of pilot funding, deny it as an outcome or ask the system to generate an email to the PI requesting them to review whether it is the result of a pilot funded project from the CTSC," said Wood. "By automating our search for publications resulting from pilot funded projects, we're able to more accurately reflect the results of our hub." PAIRS is available to all CTSA Program hubs. To learn more about the tool, please view [this webinar](#) hosted by CLIC and Weill Medical College of Cornell.

PAIRS can streamline processes for both large and small hubs. While larger hubs tend to have a greater quantity of projects and publications to keep track of, smaller hubs are often looking for ways to automate and reallocate manpower to other areas. For example, Michelle Miller, Operations Manager for Scripps Research Translational Institute says, "we are proud of the improvements we've made to our metric in the last few years and as we look for ways to continue that progress, automation is a top priority."

CTSA Program hubs rely on appropriate citations of their CTSA grant numbers as a critical performance measure when reporting on annual productivity. As such, it is crucial that hubs have a system in place that supports projects on their path to publication from start to finish. By prioritizing each of these key stages to developing pilot funded publications, hubs can fuel research growth at their institution and beyond.

Blog 3 – Insights to Inspire: Catapulting the Careers of Future Translational Scientists

In any industry, it is critically important to invest in and foster the growth of the next generation of workers. Those efforts are a particular focus within the field of translational science since it is a relatively young field of research. Providing the resources to train, cultivate and sustain future leaders of the biomedical research workforce is a key goal of the Clinical and Translational Science Award (CTSA) Program. Funded by the National Center for Advancing Translational Science (NCATS), the CTSA Program enables a coordinated, national effort to help ensure that the country will have a pipeline of trained investigators through TL1 Clinical Research Training Awards and KL2 Mentored Clinical Research Scholar Awards.

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Included in this set of metrics is the Careers Common Metric. This metric assesses the extent to which CTSA Program hubs and the consortium as a whole are training and supporting scientists to remain engaged in clinical and translational research into the future. The metric also takes into account the efforts hubs are taking to foster the growth of individuals from groups that are nationally underrepresented in the biomedical, clinical, behavioral and social sciences.

In 2019, the Common Metrics Initiative released a Multi-Year Report that identifies the hubs with the most improvement in each of the three Common Metrics for the measurement period of 2016-2017. The hubs that saw the greatest improvement in their Careers metric shared their insights on the strategies they implemented to strengthen their TL1 and KL2 award programs. A selection of these inspiring insights are outlined below to help other hubs looking for tactics to improve their own approach to clinical research training.

1. Strategic selection of scholars

Children’s Research Institute’s CTSA Program hub attributes much of the success of their KL2 program to their selection of awardees. “We have a very in-depth review process for applications, said Naomi L.C. Luban, M.D., Vice Chair of Academic Affairs, Children’s National Hospital, Children’s Research Institute and GWU School of Medicine. “Scholars submit letters of intent, which we review for quality, ingenuity and feasibility. Next, we narrow our field of applicants down to a list of potential scholars who must complete an NIH quality submission followed by an NIH simulated review, which we use to finalize our selection.” In addition to Children’s Research Institute’s careful review of the applicant and mentor team, they are also mindful of topics. The hub has found that when scholars demonstrate a personal devotion to their topic or when their topic has a

particular timeliness to current scientific innovation, scholars have more success completing their project and translating it into continuing research.

2. Regular mentorship check-ins

TL1 and KL2 awards are relatively short in timeframe. There is no buffer that would factor in any significant delays or missteps. As such, it is crucial that scholars have a support system in place to help them set goals, develop timelines and designate benchmarks to ensure they are staying on schedule.

Boston University's CTSA Program hub inaugurated two mentorship programs to help its KL2 scholars set and reach their goals. The hub initiated a career grant writing program where scholars partake in a semester long program dedicated to developing their grant writing skills. The workshops are guided by two senior faculty members that advise scholars on best practices, areas of potential concern and room for improvement with their grants. "Of the first two cohorts from this program, 100% have received K awards or career development awards from foundations allowing them to continue their work in translational science," said Dr. David Felson, Professor of Medicine and Associate Director of Boston University CTSI for Training and Education.

Boston University also launched their PRIME Program for scholars working towards RO1 or scientific grants. Similar to the career grant writing program, these are grant writing workshops that are held regularly and staffed by two senior faculty that advise scholars throughout their process of writing and pursuing grants for their research. Felson shared that "of the 13 KL2 scholars that we had when these programs started, 11 of them have their own grants. Three of them now have RO1s as principal investigators."

University of Texas Medical Branch (UTMB) Galveston also identifies mentorship as one of the key determinants of their TL1 program's success. "We have made it a priority to ensure that the mentor is comfortable challenging the goals of the mentee, said Mark Hellmich, Ph.D., Professor, UTMB. "It can often be difficult for mentors to raise red flags but given the short time frame of these grants, the ability to quickly raise issues and find strategies for addressing them can make or break a project."

3. Prioritize diversity and inclusion

As Laura Nicholson at Scripps Research Translational Institute accurately points out, investing in scholars from underrepresented groups not only improves a hub's Careers Common Metric, it also benefits the scientific research community as a whole. "Beyond simply being the right thing to do, having diverse populations involved in scientific research improves every part of the research we conduct and the education we deliver," said Nicholson. "Scripps Research's Director of Graduate Studies, Dr. Dawn Eastmond,

forged relationships and recruited to create and increase the atmosphere of diversity and inclusion that benefits all our institutional goals.”

The Medical University of South Carolina’s (MUSC) CTSA hub, the South Carolina Clinical & Translational Research Institute (SCTR), has seen particularly positive results to its TL1 program from its focus on diversity and inclusion. “We are fortunate that MUSC has made a commitment to diversity and inclusion institution-wide,” said Diana Lee-Chavarria, Education & Workforce Development Program Manager at SCTR. “Because of that commitment, we have been able to build cross-departmental connections with our Diversity and Inclusion (D&I) office, who we partner with to maximize promotional and outreach efforts.” By partnering with their D&I office to ensure they are reaching underrepresented audiences, SCTR was able to reach a larger, more comprehensive audience of potential scholars to pull from when selecting the awardee.

4. Encourage an institutional commitment to research

Children’s Research Institute also attributes the positive changes it saw in its KL2 program to the institution’s increased commitment to research as a whole. In recent years, Children’s Research Institute has made a concerted effort to hire more department heads with a focus on academia and research. “By having our faculty lead by example with their commitment to research, we were able to create an environment where 75% protected time was attainable and easy to enforce,” said Dr. Luban. “This recruitment strategy was institution wide, creating a broader base of individuals across the organization that had a clear cut commitment to clinical and translational research. This equates to more individuals for scholars to learn from, work with and look up to.”

The future of translational science will be shaped by the steps we take now to support young and developing scientists starting out in the field. By funding the right scholars and implementing creative strategies to support them in their early research, CTSA Program hubs are investing in the field and paving the way for interventions that will improve the health of individuals and the public.

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